

FE SIMULATIONS OF LARGE UD-FRP MICROSTRUCTURES UNDER LONGITUDINAL COMPRESSION

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ICCM²⁴

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Next Generation
Fibre-Reinforced Composites

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BUILDING ON PREVIOUS WORK

ECCM21: “*FE-Simulation of real microstructures: 1000 fibres, 1 mm long*”

In-depth analysis of fibre imperfections and compressive failure mechanisms.

12 hours

Aims

Why the need of 3D micromechanical FE-Models.

Importance of simulating real microstructures:

- *Why average metrics are not enough.*

Demonstration

SB FE-simulations on a LARGE CFRP microstructure with our most accurate and computationally-efficient model.

Opportunities

An in-depth analysis of compressive failure mechanisms of real FRP microstructures.

Analysis of coupled torsion-kinking behaviour of RVE.

Bonus study: Effect of real microstructures with similar average fibre imperfections.

ANALYSIS OF REAL CFRP IMPERFECTIONS

800 CF paths from μ CT (Emerson *et al.* 2017).

side view

z view

ANALYSIS OF REAL CFRP IMPERFECTIONS

800 CF paths from μ CT (Emerson *et al.* 2017).

The misalignment angle of a given fibre i is defined by its:

- i. Magnitude, θ_i^f
- ii. Planar orientation, phase angle, φ_i^f

Magnitude of fibre misalignment angle, θ_i^f

$$\overline{\theta^f} = 1.39 \pm 1.03^\circ$$

Global fibre phase angle, φ_i^f

$$\overline{\varphi^f} = -14.7^\circ$$
$$\text{IQD} = 138.9^\circ$$

ANALYSIS OF REAL CFRP IMPERFECTIONS

800 CF paths from μ CT (Emerson *et al.* 2017)

- A distribution of fibre diameters is assumed due to lack of available tracking data;

- A normal distribution with:

$$\overline{\varnothing^f} = 6.6 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{m}^*$$

Distribution of fibres diameter, \varnothing^f [μm]

* Experimentally obtained standard deviation for similar fibre type (Mesquita *et al.* 2021)

ANALYSIS OF REAL CFRP IMPERFECTIONS

800 CF paths from μ CT (Emerson *et al.* 2017)

- The local fibre volume fraction of the RVE (V^f) is calculated employing the Voronoi Network for each Z section;

- A large variation in V^f is observed \rightarrow $\overline{V^f} = 49.2 \pm 8.4 \%$

Local fibre volume fraction, V^f

SIMULATING REAL CFRP-RVEs

Matrix: Yield-band

Fibres: Fibre kinking

SIMULATING REAL CFRP-RVEs

- A 3D torsional deformation occurs and becomes more pronounced during matrix yielding.
- The direction of torsion is not constant.

Fibres

Matrix

FRAME BY FRAME ANALYSIS

FIBRE MOTION – PEAK GLOBAL STRESS

Fibre motion can be decoupled to kinking and **torsional** motion
A small ($\sim 1.25^\circ$) but perfect circular motion is observed.

Key questions:

“What drives the torsional deformation?”

“Why is this even important?”

FIBRE TWISTING – PEAK GLOBAL STRESS

Torsional deformation potentially occurs because of the initial twist of fibre architecture!

ASSESSMENT OF FIBRE TWISTING

Decouple the mean misalignment from mean twisting of fibres.

The average twisting angle of the initial fibre architecture:

$$\overline{\Psi_0^f} = 16.4^\circ$$

Case study: Effect of real fibre imperfections

Compressive failure in RVEs with similar microstructural features

To be continued at my talk...

RVE 1

RVE 2

RVEs with 600 fibres and $L = 450 \mu\text{m}$ but in different region in the CT specimen

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<https://nextcomp.ac.uk>

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